

The Contribution of Focusing Attention to the Development of the Performance of Athletes with Visual Impairments for Goal Ball from the Point of View of the Algerian Coach

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Abstract

The study aims to identify the focus of attention and its contribution to improving the performance of visually impaired Algerian goal ball athletes. For this purpose, we used a descriptive method on a sample consisting of 7 Algerian coaches from the first national division who were purposefully selected. We used a questionnaire, and after collecting and statistically processing the results, we found that attention focus skill has an impact on the performance of goal ball players and is considered important for performance improvement. This confirmed to us that attention focus contributes to enhancing athletes' performance. The researchers recommend that coaches and psychological specialists pay more attention to developing the attention focus skill of players in order to improve their performance.

Keywords: *Attention Span; the Performance; Visual Impairment; Goal Ball.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Psychological preparation techniques represent an important dimension in preparing players as they play a fundamental role in developing performance, so they are now viewed as one of the variables that must be taken care of alongside physical, technical and tactical requirements. International sports champions are very similar in terms of physical, technical and tactical level, and the psychological factor determines the players' results during the competition as it plays a major role in achieving victory. (Alawi, 1999, p. 35)

Al-Arabi Shmoon points out that developing psychological traits using psychological preparation techniques, which include relaxation, focus, mental visualization, vital feedback, etc., must go hand in hand with developing physical fitness elements through long- and short-term programs and must be focused on. (Shmoon, 1996, p. 362)

Psychological skills are among the most important factors that affect sports performance, whether in the process of motor and skill learning or in preparing the player from the mental and psychological side in order to confront various situations and positions. (Al-Arabi, 2023, p. 278) Mental preparations play a major role in an individual reaching the highest possible level (Saghiri and Idir, 2019, p. 14), and in this study we took one of the higher mental processes, which is focusing attention, as it is one of the basic requirements for good performance in any type of sports activity.

Coaches emphasize the importance of focusing attention in contributing to achieving optimal performance. Focusing attention is defined as focusing the focus of attention on the signs associated with performance in the surrounding environment and maintaining this focus for a period of time that achieves the possession of temporary cognitive awareness. (Jawani, Shrit, and Hadi, 2021, p. 54)

The category of people with visual disabilities is the person who loses his sight, losing a main channel of his communication with the world around him and becomes forced to rely on other senses (Al-Beblawy and Ahmed, 2014, p. 193). Bell ball is one of the sports activities that are loved by the blind and was specially developed for them to suit the nature of the performance in it and the type of disability. The skill performance in it depends on the sense of hearing in the first degree (Ali and Abu Al-Layl, 2005, page 276).

By watching some bell ball matches, the researchers noticed that sometimes the player throws the ball off its path when throwing it. During the conversation with the player, they attributed this to lack of focus and attention. The researchers saw that this is related to weak focus of attention as one of the important mental abilities required by the visually impaired player, in addition to the methods and training techniques used with this category of players.

They are simple traditional methods, because the trainers responsible for the training process rely on personal experience without relying on the precise scientific aspects in developing appropriate training programs for this category, with the absence of a study in the field of bell ball for the visually impaired regarding focus of attention. Most of the previous research and studies focused on the visually impaired who are not athletes in various aspects (social, recreational, psychological, ...) and did not address the sports aspect and its importance for this category of the disabled in general and in bell ball in particular.

Here we have identified the problem of our study and tried to find appropriate solutions for it by developing the focus of attention for visually impaired bell ball players and observing the extent to which the results of this development contribute to the performance of some basic skills of this game, to be a clear indicator that works to help coaches and specialists in this field to plan the training process in accordance with the scientific method appropriate to the levels of blind players to achieve the best achievements at various local and international sports levels, and from this standpoint the general question crystallized: Does the focus of attention contribute to improving the performance of Algerian bell ball athletes from the point of view of coaches?

This question branches into the following sub-questions:

1. Does training the skill of focusing attention have an effect on the performance of bell ball players?
2. Is focusing attention important to improve the performance of bell ball players in Algerian teams?

2. HYPOTHESES:

The researchers seek to verify the following hypotheses:

2.1 General hypothesis:

The focus of attention contributes to improving the performance of Algerian bell ball athletes from the point of view of coaches.

2.2 Partial hypotheses:

1. Training the skill of focusing attention has an impact on the performance of bell ball players.
2. Focusing attention is important to improve the performance of bell ball players in Algerian teams.

3. STUDY OBJECTIVES

The main objective of the research can be limited to being a study of the psychological aspect of the athlete, specifically the focus of attention of the player during his practice of sports activity, highlighting through it the role of focusing attention in improving the player's performance. There are sub-objectives derived from the main objective of the research, which are:

- Knowing whether training the skill of focusing attention has an impact on the performance of bell ball players.
- Discovering that the skill of focusing attention is important to improve the performance of bell ball players in Algerian teams

4. IMPORTANCE OF THE STUDY

This study is of great importance in terms of training strategy and organized and planned work in sports training. The topic of focusing attention is considered one of the most important topics that teams pay great attention to. Through focusing attention, results vary and performance differs. In this study, we will try to show that focusing attention is a pillar of the pillars on which modern sports training depends in order to improve the level of performance, as well as highlighting the role of focusing attention in learning and acquiring skills and methods of applying it in training and competition in order to prepare the player for sports tournaments, especially bell ball teams. The importance of the study also lies in:

- Describing the focus of attention in Algerian bell ball teams.
- Revealing obstacles to the general development of sports performance.
- Trying to draw the attention of researchers at this level to this topic in order to deepen research in it.
- We shed light on the importance and role of the skill of focusing attention in improving the athlete's performance.

5. DEFINING THE TERMS OF THE STUDY

5.1 Focus of attention:

5.1.1. Language:

Pay attention/pay attention to:

Meaning focusing the mind and limiting it to one interest, or in one of the fields leads to its clarity. (Amel, 1981, p. 67)

5.1.2. Technically:

The term focus of attention refers to the accumulation of mental energy and its focused direction towards a specific idea or one of the contents of motor memory. (Arousi and Saudi, 2022, p. 373)

It is the limitation of attention to a specific stimulus for a specific period of time.

This occurs by completely disconnecting from the external environment to perform a motor performance or carry out a precise task by collecting mental processes for a short period of time because they are stressful for the mind.

The closest example of this is throwing of all kinds, weightlifting, and swimming.

The above can be explained by the fact that attention is the collection of all ideas and intellectual processes at one point to serve the skillful work to be achieved.

Focus of attention is a term that refers to the accumulation of mental energy and its focused direction towards a specific idea or one of the contents of motor memory or a specific subject so that mental energy is focused on it or directed towards it.

On the other hand, the brain formulates and interprets the external stimuli reaching it and selects some of them. In this case, the cerebral cortex coordinates the necessary sensory-motor information. (Marzouq, 2000, p. 78)

5.1.3. Procedurally:

Attention is one of the higher mental processes that plays an important role in human life. It helps us to know things, quickly understand them and focus on them. It is also one of the psychological processes that occur in a specific part of the brain through neural activity. The world surrounding the individual is full of many stimuli and stimuli that come from different sources at once, as they compete with each other, attracting the individual's attention at every moment of wakefulness. However, he cannot pay attention to all of them, but rather chooses some of them in a circle whose center is one of the stimuli, surrounded by the rest of the stimuli far from the center of attention, so he pays attention to them. In this study, the sensory stimulus is the stimulus that the bell ball player relies on.

5.2. Performance:**5.2.1. Language:**

Achievement, performance, shooting, behavior, payment. (Khalaf, 2008, p. 66).

5.2.2. Technically:

It is the worker's efficiency in his work and his behavior in it, and the extent of his suitability to carry out the burdens of his work, and bear responsibility (Hamad, 2001, p. 89).

5.2.3. Procedurally:

It is the individual's ability to bear his responsibility as the burden of work assigned to him within a specific period of time.

5.3. Visual impairment:

5.3.1. Linguistically:

It requires us to divide the phrase into two words: "disability" and "visual", as disability: according to Larousse is: "a deficiency that makes its owner in a state of deficiency", (Larousse, 1977, p. 154), as for visual: It is a quality taken from the source of "vision" the sense of sight, the eye, knowledge, and the plural of sight, and the sighted is the one who is able to see, unlike the blind, (Al-Bustani, 1956, p. 34)

5.3.2. Technically:

The inability of the eye to see and requires the use of other senses in the learning and training processes. (Saad Ali and Abu Al-Layl, 2005, page 265).

5.3.3. Procedurally:

It is a state of total or partial loss of sight that affects the individual in performing his tasks as he relies on his other senses.

5.4. Bell ball:

5.4.1. Language:

It is divided into two words:

Ball:

Round objects made of rubber or leather that children play with in sports games (Jibran, 1992, page 663), and Bell: A hollow tool made of copper or the like that is used to summon a person, a voice, a hidden voice (Jibran, 1992, page 272).

5.4.2. Technically:

Goalball is a game for the blind, played by two teams, each team consisting of three players, and each team has the right to three substitutions. The goalball game is played on a sports hall floor measuring 18 meters by 9 meters, and the field is divided into two halves by a center line. Each team remains in its designated half of the field during the match. The goal of this game is to throw the ball with the hand across the hall to reach the goal line of the opposing team, while the opposing team tries to prevent it from reaching its goal (Hendawi, 2017, p. 11).

5.4.3. Procedurally:

Bell ball is a group game directed at visually impaired players of various degrees. Each team includes three players, on a field marked with prominent lines to help the players. It is played with a ball with a bell, and the two teams compete to score the largest number of goals under the rules of the game.

6. EXPLORATORY STUDY

The researcher used this study as a beginning for his work to identify the negatives that may accompany the sample's answer to the questionnaire and overcome them for the safety of the basic procedures of the research. Qasim Al-Mandlawi says that thanks to conducting the exploratory study, the researcher can know the negatives that the testees went through and overcome them in the next test. (Al-Mandlawi, 1989, page 108) Therefore, the researcher distributed the questionnaire to 4 trainers from the second section to know the difficulties that he may face in his basic work. Hassan Abu Ubayya says in this regard: The test must be under

trial to prove its validity, taking into account the degree of objectivity, the coefficient of validity, and the degree of stability. (Abu Ubayya, 1977, page 39)

6.1. Study Methodology:

Choosing the method is an important stage of scientific research, as the nature of the method determines how to collect data and information about the subject under study. Therefore, there is a direct relationship between the method and the subject of the study, as well as the research problem, as the nature of the subject determines the method used. Since the study at hand is to highlight the role of focusing attention in improving the performance of a bell ball athlete, we adopted the descriptive method in its survey method, which Bashir Saleh Al-Rashidi considers a set of research procedures that complement each other to describe the phenomenon or subject based on collecting facts and data, classifying them, processing them, and analyzing them with sufficient and accurate analysis to extract their significance and reach results or generalizations on the phenomenon or subject that is the subject of the research. (Al-Rashidi, 2000, p. 59)

6.2 Study community and sample:

6.2.1 Study community:

The research community is considered a frame of reference for the researcher in choosing the research sample. This frame may be a large or small community, and the frame may be individuals, schools, universities, or sports clubs (Ibrahim, 2006, p. 95).

The study community is represented by the group of active coaches in the first national division of bell ball in Algeria.

6.2.2 Study sample: The sample is a number of individuals who make up the community from which it was taken to represent it. The validity of the sample's representation of the community depends on the method of its selection and its size. (Al-Tayeb, 1999, p. 20).

The sample of our study was represented by the coaches of the Algerian bell ball teams in the first division of the national championship.

6.3. Sample selection:

The sample was chosen intentionally.

6.3.1 Sample characteristics:

A- Number of sample members: The research sample included 12 coaches who train teams from the first national division.

B- Age determination: Their age ranged between 37 and 52 years

7. STATISTICAL TOOL

The statistical data were processed using the SPSS statistical package program, version 21, where the processing included the following statistical methods: percentage and coefficient (Ka2). By determining the research methodology that includes choosing the method used in this study as well as the sample from our research community applied to it.

8. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

8.1. Presentation and analysis of the results:

8.1.1. Presentation and analysis of the results of the first hypothesis:

Which states that training the skill of focusing attention has an effect on the performance of bell ball players.

Question 1: Does the skill of focusing attention that you do work to reduce the effort and time spent in training?

Purpose of the question: To know whether the skill of focusing attention works to reduce the effort and time spent in training.

Table 1: Shows whether the skill of focusing attention works to reduce the effort and time spent.

Statistical Significance	Significance	Q2	Sig	Percentage	Frequency	Answer
Function	0.05	12	0.01	100%	12	YES
				00%	0	NO
				100%	12	the total

Figure 1: Shows whether the skill of focusing attention reduces the effort and time expended.

9. ANALYSIS

By reviewing the results of Table 1, we note that the percentage of the yes answer was estimated at 100%, the value of Chi-square was estimated at 12, and the value of Sig was 0.01, which is less than the significance level of 0.05, which means that there are statistically significant differences. From the table, we note that all trainers answered yes, which means that they see that the skill of focusing attention that they practice reduces the effort and time spent in training. From this, we conclude that the skill of focusing attention that the trainer practices reduces the effort and time spent in training. 9- Discussion of the results:

9.1 Discussion of the results of the first hypothesis:

Through the results obtained, it was found that training the skill of focusing attention has an effect on the performance of bell ball players, as the researcher believes that these results are logical because they are consistent with several studies, including the results of the study

(Saeedi and Shernin, 2020), which confirms that the skill of focusing attention is an essential skill to improve the performance of Saudi referees in football. The study (Khadhravi and Shuwayya, 2018) also indicated the existence of a relationship between both motor abilities and cognitive mental abilities (focus of attention), in addition to other studies that the researcher reviewed, such as the study (Jawani, Sharit, and Hadi, 2021), which confirmed the existence of a correlation between the level of focus of attention and the accuracy of short serve in badminton. Through all of this, it must be noted that it is necessary to pay attention to practicing motor education in the primary stage.

These results are explained based on several reasons, foremost of which is that focusing attention, which is considered one of the basic skills of learning, refers to: the period during which the player can focus on a specific topic, and attention requires the player's ability to focus on topics Unnecessary, and therefore the player's weak ability to distinguish between what is necessary and what is unnecessary leads to difficulties in paying attention to information and events related to the subject.

Attention is one of the important human powers in an individual's life, in terms of his ability to communicate with the surrounding environment, which is reflected in his choice of various appropriate sensory stimuli so that he can perceive and analyze them accurately, and respond to them in a way that reflects his compatibility with his internal and external environment, as attention is the main process in directing the individual's awareness in various behavioral situations, as it is the process through which he acquires many skills, and forms many behavioral habits that achieve a great deal of compatibility in the environment in which he lives, and this is what matches the focus of attention and the test of the strength distinguished by speed, as the relationship between mental ability and the physical test subject came positive and statistically significant, and therefore the first hypothesis is achieved.

9.2 Discussion of the results of the second hypothesis:

Through the results obtained, it became clear that focusing attention is important to improve the performance of the bell ball player, as the researcher believes that these results are logical because they are consistent with several studies, including the study (Rahmoun, Salmi, and Bouassida, 2021), which stated that the secret to the success of many coaches is the interest in developing psychological skills, including focusing attention, and he also recommended paying attention to it because it is related to most skills, as stated in the study (Al-Arabi, 2023) that there are statistically significant differences in the skill of focusing attention and the skill of lateral throwing in favor of the experimental sample, and this confirms that focusing attention is important for the player's performance, so the researcher recommended using modern and innovative methods of training as well as with regard to focusing attention, and through what was presented, it became clear to us that the second hypothesis is achieved. 10.

Conclusions and suggestions: The process of preparing an athlete aims to bring the player to the highest level, and the more he is characterized by good qualification, the more he masters knowledge and methods of applying it and mastering it, and focusing attention in a scientific and practical way contributes greatly to developing and growing the athlete's level to the maximum degree. The prevailing belief is that physical, technical and tactical preparations alone are sufficient to raise the level of players' performance, but what we have reached is the opposite, or rather that focusing attention has an effective impact on the level of players' performance, especially when it comes to bell ball, and this requires great attention to focusing attention, finding a way for harmony, coordination and unification of efforts to achieve the

goal, which is victory. Because of the importance and impact of focusing attention on the psychology of the bell ball player by developing his competencies, improving his performance and improving their ability to confront the problems and obstacles that they encounter throughout their practice of the sport to achieve the highest level of player performance, which ensures successful participation in various tournaments and sports events. After completing the study, it was found that research on the topic of attention focus is still worthy of interest and research, including:

- The effectiveness of attention focus in improving the skill and tactical performance of bell ball players.
- The coach's behavior and its effect on attention focus and the athletic level of bell ball players.
- Not neglecting attention focus in bell ball as an important factor in improving performance and achieving positive athletic results.
- The necessity of subjecting players to situations and conditions similar to match conditions during some training units to accustom players to dealing with different situations with high levels of attention and on an ongoing basis.

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